

RESISTANCE OF NICKEL-COATED THERMALLY CYCLED COMPOSITES TO LUNAR DUST ABRASION

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1 Introduction

At the time of the Apollo missions, structural components sent to the Moon were mostly made of aluminum or other metallic materials. Composites offer a lightweight alternative with a low coefficient of thermal expansion. However, previous work done at the Canadian Space Agency [1] has shown that composites offer little resistance to lunar dust. In lunar exploration, dust poses a significant problem due to its pervasiveness, adherence, and abrasiveness, causing premature failures of structures, as it was learned during the Apollo missions [2]. The current work focuses on the resistance of high Young's modulus carbon fiber composites suited for the space environment, M55J/RS3, basically a PAN fiber in a cyanate ester resin, coated with nanocrystalline nickel as a dust resistance mitigation measure. The samples were exposed to thermal cycles from -196°C to 130°C for 10 cycles. Young's modulus, hardness, and resistance to abrasion for the coated samples are compared to the properties of the non-coated samples. The set-up consists of a sand blasting bench that has been adapted for the emulated lunar dust CHENOBI. These experimental results give a first evaluation of the suitability of space grade nickel coated composites for use in the lunar environment as structural components.

2 Lunar Environment

The lunar environment is an extreme one that poses challenges to the design of structures. Lunar days and nights last 14 earth days each and temperatures vary from extremes of 120°C during the day to -150°C at night in the most common exploration areas, with extremes of -230°C in the polar craters [3]. Structures must accommodate large temperature

swings that occur rapidly during the change from day to night and vice versa.

The dust, the lunar regolith, is an additional challenge. It adheres strongly to all surfaces. The mechanical aspect of adhesion is due to the jagged shape of regolith particles as shown in Figure 1. The absence of an atmosphere means there is no wind that would otherwise smooth regolith particles, resulting in sharp edges [4]. While Figure 1 shows a fairly large particle, most particles are below 70 µm diameter; particles in this size range can infiltrate and abrade almost all mechanical systems, and will even abrade mechanical seals [7].

Regolith contains a small fraction of iron, 0.77% in mass [5]. However, this iron is in the form of nanophase-size (3 to 33nm) iron particle present in all dust particles [6]. Lunar dust then becomes very sensitive to electrostatic charging. The particles get charged by the solar wind in the day and plasma electron currents at night and this leads to electrostatic adhesion [2]. This electrostatic charging enables particles to cling to ungrounded conductive surfaces and nonconductive surfaces. The solar wind charges the particles positively during daytime, and the electron plasma currents charge the particles negatively at night. Finer regolith grains will levitate under electrostatic charging and therefore, the dust is present at instrument level, even in the absence of any mechanical disturbance of the soil. This makes the dust highly pervasive, even a few meters above the ground.

In contrast, the emulated lunar dust, CHENOBI, contains iron, up to 1-2% of the composition [8]. These iron particles are mixed with the dust, but not aggregated to it. Consequently, the emulated lunar dust does not react exactly like real regolith when

submitted to electrostatic charging or a magnetic field. Experiments done with the emulated lunar dust will only replicate certain aspects of the behavior of lunar dust.

Fig. 1. Lunar regolith particle

Image Credit: David S. McKay, NASA/JSC, Permission Granted.

Any lunar vehicle will displace an important quantity of dust while moving. The dust propelled by the wheel will erode the structure of the vehicle itself or other structures around. The Apollo Lunar Rovers were driven at a speed of up to 13 km/h with a normal cruise speed of 6-7 km/h [3]. The lower gravity and the absence of atmosphere, combined with the electrostatic properties of the dust, all contributed to projecting the dust with considerable velocity and little attenuation. The extreme example is a landing on the Moon that ejects dust particles at low angles at a speed of 2000 m/s, seriously eroding any surface in the vicinity [9]. Dust is a major concern when considering the lunar environment, and materials used for lunar applications must have the required survivability.

3 Erosion of M55J/RS3

In a preceding paper [1], we looked at the erosion of a M55J/RS3 composite. The space grade laminates, procured from Composites Atlantic Limited, are made of high modulus carbon fibers (M55J) [10] with toughened polycyanate resin (RS3) [11]. The laminates consist of four plies with a fiber orientation

of 0/45/90/135°. The average thickness is 0.43mm. Properties are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Composite material properties

Property	Fiber M55J	Resin RS3
Tensile strength	4020 MPa	80 MPa
Tensile Modulus	540 GPa	2.96 GPa
Density	1.91g/cm ³	1.19g/cm ³
Volume content	60%	40%

The rate of erosion was quite high. Sixty grams of emulated lunar dust were used on the samples with an impact angle of 30°, and twenty grams with an impact angle of 90°. Since the erosion rate with respect to the impact angle is not a linear behavior [12], it is not possible to extrapolate the results. The erosion was more severe for the 90° impact angle. Using a third of the emulated lunar dust generated half the erosion seen at 30°, which is typical of the erosion behavior of a brittle material [12]. There is not a definite consensus of how to define the brittle or ductile behavior of composites under erosion. Part of the difficulty arises from the fact that the composite behavior under erosion will vary with the erosion factors, such as impact velocity, particle flux, or particle properties. The interest in defining the behavior is to predict what happens under ongoing erosion. A brittle material will show a higher material loss when impacted at 90°, and the material loss will be proportional to time of exposure to the abrasive particles. A ductile material will show maximum material loss when impacted at an angle of 30°, but will go through a phase where the particles will embed themselves in the composite. As the bombardment goes on, the mass loss will resume a linear behavior with exposure time. Some authors have also observed semi-ductile behavior where the material loss is maximized for an impacting angle of 60°. Most authors, though, report that thermosetting composites, such as the one used in this paper, present a brittle behavior under erosion.

The erosion observed for the M55J/RS3 was quite superior to the one seen for aluminum [1] and concerns were raised on the use of composites for lunar missions in conditions where it would be subjected to projected dust. This led us to investigate

coatings which could provide erosion protection, while being suitable for the space environment.

4 Nickel Coated Samples

A Canadian company, Integran, is producing a nickel based coating that increases resistance to erosion. The coating consists of grains of 20µm or less of a ferrous nickel alloy. It has shown promises for tooling and has already been applied on composites. A layer of an average thickness of 75µm was deposited on M55/RS3 samples. The thickness can be approximated based on the manufacturing process, but destructive tests are needed to measure the coating thickness. Two coatings were experimented with: Nanovate N1010 (nNi) and NanovateN2035 (nNiFe), which contains a higher proportion of iron than Nanovate N1010. Properties are presented in Table 2, as per the manufacturer. These samples were thermally cycled, from -196°C to +130°C for 10 cycles, and then submitted to the same erosion testing as the pure composite samples. Figures 2 to 5 show a sample before the erosion test with increasing levels of details. The square in Figure 2 is the section used for the electron microscope observation.

Table 2. Coating properties

Property	Nanovate N1010	Nanovate N2035
Hardness	400 VHN	450 VHN
Yield strength	790 MPa	1100 MPa
Tensile strength	1300 MPa	1600 MPa
Young's Modulus	150 GPa	110 GPa
Poisson' Ratio	0.31	0.30
CTE	13.6 ppm/°c	6-7 ppm/°C
Density	8.9 g/cm ³	8.4 g/cm ³

Fig. 2. N2035 sample before test

Fig. 3. N2035 sample cross section (before test)

Fig. 4. N2035 surface 30x (before test)

Fig. 5. N2035 surface 100x (before test)

5 Test set-up

The experiment and protocol are the same as the ones presented in the previous paper [1]. The erosion testing was performed at 30° and 90°. The amount of emulated lunar dust projected on the samples was 60g for both impingement angles. When the bare samples were tested, at an impingement angle of 90°, only 20g were used, since a 60g quantity would lead to making a hole in the samples. Three samples of each coating type were tested. As shown in Figure 6, a sandblast cabinet was used to safely prevent dust from escaping and making contact with skin or lungs. The apparatus used for the erosion testing was placed inside the cabinet. Emulated lunar dust was stocked in the funnel, and a vacuum cleaner was used to remove the levitating dust from the cabinet.

Fig. 6. Propelling dust apparatus

The test setup is presented in Figure 7. The sample holder can be rotated about the impact center to vary

the impact angle. The distance between the nozzle and the sample was set to 100mm and the air pressure was controlled with a regulator. The speed of the particles was estimated to be 38 m/s (driving gas pressure of 275 kPa) based on the speed of the air without the emulated lunar dust, measured using an anemometer.

Fig. 7. Regolith simulant projection test setup

6 Emulated Lunar Dust

The emulated lunar dust used was the CHENOBI one, which is highly representative of the abrasive properties of the actual lunar dust [8][13]. The CHENOBI is composed of glass at 53% and plagioclase at 44% (which include Aluminum at 17% and Calcium at 11 %). Figure 8 shows a macroscopic view of the CHENOBI dust used for the experiment. The particles have a crystalline nature with sharp edges. One particle can be clearly identified (300µm) on the right side of the picture. The other particles are much smaller (0.1µm to 50µm).

Fig. 8. CHENOBI particle

7 Test results

The erosion test was performed for both coatings at 30° and 90° impingement. For all the samples, the projected emulated lunar dust did not go through the coating. An additional test was done on the last sample of both series to see if the coating could resist to a second dust projection and it effectively survived. Table 3 presents the result for a 30° impingement angle.

Table 3. Erosion rate at 30°

Angle: 30°	Sample	Erosion rate (mg/60g)
N1010	44	17.2
	45	15.2
	46	14.6
	46 (second pass)	13.5
N2035	54	17.0
	55	19.2
	57	19.4
	57 (second pass)	25.8

The test results presented in the previous paper were giving an erosion rate, at 30° for the composite without coating, of 115mg of eroded material for 60g of dust projected, and for the aluminum, of 6.3mg of eroded material for 60g of dust projected.

The erosion rates for the coated sample are now much closer to the ones of the aluminum sample.

Figure 9 shows Sample 57, a sample with a nickel iron coating, after the erosion test. The surface is uniform, and the surface is not as glossy as the one shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 9. Sample 57

Figure 10 shows that the grains are not visible when compared to the un-tested sample shown in Figure 4. The dark spot is either a particle of simulant or a hole in the coating. The observation under the microscope and the energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis performed was unable to confirm the nature of the spot. EDS peaks other than the expected ones for the nickel coating were not predominant. It was impossible to conclude that these spots were bare composite. On other samples, we were able to confirm that these types of spots were areas where there was no coating left.

Fig. 10. Sample 57 at 30x

The cross section, shown in Figure 11, was taken at the center of the impact region. The thickness of the remaining coating is uniform. Since it was not possible to measure the coating thickness before the test (a destructive test would be needed), the thickness of the remaining coating cannot be compared to the one before testing. However, the coating after erosion testing is thinner than the primer, which was not the case before erosion testing as can be seen in Figure 3.

Fig. 11: Sample 57 cross-section

Table 4 presents the result at a 90° impingement angle.

Table 4. Erosion rate at 90°

Angle: 90°	Sample	Erosion rate (mg/60g)
N1010	42	2.8
	43	3.1
	47	3.2
	47 (second pass)	5.9
N2035	52	17.3*
	53	7.0
	58	6.6
	58 (second pass)	7.5

* Outlier result

The test results presented in the previous paper [1] were showing an erosion rate, at 90°, for the composite without coating, of 56 mg of material loss for a 20g of projected emulated lunar dust. For

aluminum, there was a gain of 1mg for 60g of projected emulated lunar dust. This gain in mass is indicating that the aluminum was in its phase of absorption of impinging materials, as is the case for ductile materials. Table 4 shows that the coating clearly improves the erosion rates, by reducing the 56 mg of material loss for 20g of projected emulated lunar dust, to a few grams of material loss for 60g of projected lunar dust, a major improvement.

Figure 12 shows Sample 58, a sample coated with a nickel iron alloy, after the erosion test. Sample 58 is being eroded with an impingement angle of 90°. Small wrinkles can be seen on the surface at the center of the impacted region. These surface deformations are clearly seen on the cross section view shown on Figure 14.

Fig. 12. Sample 58 – nickel iron coating impacted at 90°

Just as was the case for the samples eroded with an angle of 30°, Figure 13 shows some dark spot at the surface of the nickel iron coated sample eroded at an angle of 90°. Again, this is either a particle of emulated lunar dust or a hole in the coating. The observation under the microscope and the energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis performed did not lead to a conclusion on the nature of the spot.

Fig. 13. Sample 58 - nickel iron coating impacted at 90° magnified at 30x

Fig. 14. Sample 58 cross-section - nickel iron coating impacted at 90°

8 Discussion

The samples eroded with an angle of 90° have shown a good resistance to erosion, very similar to the ones obtained for aluminum. The erosion rate was greater than for the samples eroded with a 30° angle, which is typical of a ductile material behavior.

Ductile materials, such as nickel, will absorb some of the impingement particles when submitted to erosion. The absorption is worst at 90° compared to 30°. The following figures present the energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analysis for the samples presented previously. The EDS analysis for the non eroded sample, shown in Figure 15, displays

only nickel (Ni) and iron (Fe) as components, which are the elements found in the coating material. Figure 16 looks at Sample 57, a composite sample coated with a nickel iron alloy and eroded with an angle of 30°. Traces of aluminum (Al) and silicon (Si) are found, which shows that some emulated lunar dust particles are absorbed, since these elements are found in the emulated lunar dust and not in the coating. Figure 17 shows the EDS for Sample 58, a composite sample coated with a nickel iron alloy eroded at 90°. Aluminium, silicon, and calcium (Ca) are found in a greater proportion than what is the case for the 30° impingement angle. This confirms that the coating is behaving as a ductile material.

Chemical formula	ms%	mol%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
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Fig. 15. EDS analysis before erosion for the nickel iron alloy coated composite

Fig. 16. EDS analysis for the nickel iron alloy coated composite with an impingement angle of 30°

Fig. 17. EDS analysis for the nickel iron alloy coated composite with an impingement angle of 90°

Particles on the surface of a coating will change the surface thermal properties (reflectivity, solar absorptivity, and IR emissivity). As mentioned earlier, the magnetic properties of lunar dust are not adequately represented by the emulated lunar regolith. On the moon, the particles will adhere to the surface, which will have an even higher impact on the thermal properties. Evaluation of the thermal

properties before being eroded and after erosion is being currently done.

1.1 Comparison with an Aluminium Panel

The main advantage of the carbon fiber composite material over aluminum for a honeycomb panel is the mass, low CTE, and high stiffness. The coating helps the composite resist to erosion, but the added mass from the primer and coating reduces the mass advantage of the carbon fiber composite. In order to compare composite material to aluminum for the mass, the equivalent thickness of aluminum required to obtain the same stiffness as the composite must be evaluated.

Even if the coating has a high modulus, the coating is so thin that it won't influence the overall modulus of the coated sample. The uncoated sample has a modulus of 100 GPa as obtained by test [1] and 150 GPa for the nickel alloy coating, as stated by the manufacturer. Analytical calculation and preliminary test results show that the modulus increase due to the coating is negligible. The modulus of the coated sample is approximately 105 GPa. The equivalent aluminium thickness needed to have the same stiffness would be 0.769mm, compared to 0.620mm for the coated sample. The surface density of the coated sample is 1.23kg/m² and the surface density of the equivalent thickness of aluminium is 2.08kg/m². The uncoated composite has a surface density of 0.615 kg/m². Without the coating, the composite represents a mass reduction compared to aluminium of 70%. With the coating, the mass reduction drops to 41%, which is still an appreciable mass gain from a mission perspective. Coating only areas submitted to intense abrasion would increase the mass gain.

1.2 Other Advantages of the Coating

Other than the advantages mentioned earlier, the conductive coating will improve to various levels the surface charging, the electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), the reduction of electromagnetic interference (EMI), and radiation protection compared to an uncoated sample. The small thickness of the coating will be sufficient to prevent surface charging, but it may have a limited impact on the EMC/EMI. The thickness will have a filtering effect on the electromagnetic wave frequency, but a

thicker coating will be required for a better protection over a large frequency band. The EMC/EMI and radiation protections will probably be less effective than the ones gained with aluminum, but can still be sufficient to warrant the use of a coated carbon fiber composite. No tests were performed to quantify the surface charging, EMC/EMI, and radiation protection.

9 Conclusions and Future Work

This work has shown that a nickel alloy coating with a low CTE can protect composites from erosion, producing a material with the advantage of aluminium with respect to abrasive lunar dust, but with the added benefits of a low CTE and stability under large temperature excursions. Future work will involve evaluating the thermal properties of the nickel coated samples to evaluate their structural use for lunar applications.

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